

Effect of Non-Electrolytes on the Precipitation of Thorium Hydroxide from its Salt Solution in Presence of Alkali.

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Dhar (*Kolloid Z.*, 1923, 33, 193), Mehrotra (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 117) and Sen (*ibid.*, 1927, 4, 131) have studied the peptisation of various metallic hydroxides in presence of sugars in a semi-quantitative way. Kuhn and Pirsch (*Kolloid Z.*, 1925, 36, 310) have made a detailed study of the peptisation of bismuth hydroxide in presence of several sugars. The inhibition of the precipitation of thorium hydroxide in presence of non-electrolytes when caustic soda solution is added to a salt solution of thorium has not yet been studied. It was, therefore, decided to try the effect of non-electrolytes on the precipitation of thorium hydroxide.

An approximately $N/20$ solution of thorium nitrate was prepared and the amount of thorium per 100 c.c. of the solution was then estimated by precipitating as hydroxide and weighing as thorium oxide. A stock solution of caustic soda was also prepared and standardised against oxalic acid. Glycerol and other non-electrolytes, except urea and cane sugar, used in these experiments were purified by redistillation.

The minimum amount of the non-electrolyte necessary to prevent the appearance of the hydroxide of the metal was determined as follows:—

A known volume of the salt solution was taken in a number of test tubes and mixed with varying amounts of the non-electrolyte. In a number of other sets of test tubes a definite amount of alkali was diluted with the calculated amount of water in order to make the total volume (salt solution + non-electrolyte + alkali + water) 25 c.c. The contents of the two sets of test tubes were mixed throughout in a uniform manner. The amounts of the non-electrolyte necessary to prevent the instantaneous appearance of the precipitate of thorium hydroxide were very carefully determined. Experiments were repeated twice and the mean value was taken in

all the cases. The amount of alkali added was greater than what would have been required for the complete precipitation of the hydroxide. The non-electrolytes tried were cane sugar, glycerol acetone, methyl, ethyl and isopropyl alcohols and urea. It was found that only cane sugar and glycerol prevented the appearance of the hydroxide.

Effect of the Concentration of the Salt Solution.

Table I contains the results which show the effect of the addition of different amounts of the salt on the inhibition of the precipitation of its hydroxide in presence of cane sugar and glycerol.

TABLE I.

Total volume = 25 c.c. NaOH = 0.6 millimole.

Thorium nitrate (in millimoles).	Cane sugar sufficient to prevent precipitation. (in millimoles).	Glycerol sufficient to prevent precipitation. (in millimoles).
0.00768	1.24	13.7
0.01536	1.64	28.77
0.02304	3.25	71.38
0.03072	5.84	120.83
0.03840	9.62	173.62
0.04608	13.75	—

It is seen from the table that cane sugar is a better inhibiting agent than glycerol. The inhibition of the precipitation of the metallic hydroxide is due to the adsorption of the non-electrolyte and the greater the adsorption of a non-electrolyte, the greater should be its inhibitive power. The fact that the alcohols do not inhibit the precipitation of the hydroxide even when added in large amounts leads one to postulate that the number of hydroxyl groups in the non-electrolyte has something to do with the inhibition of the precipitation of the hydroxide. This view is supported by the results because cane sugar acts as a better inhibiting agent than glycerol due to its having eight OH-groups. The effect of alcohols was negligible because they contain only one OH-group. Urea and acetone have no OH-groups and, therefore, they could not act as inhibiting agents.

According to Graham, the solutions which are formed by the addition of caustic soda to a salt solution of copper or iron in presence of sugar, contain the sucrates of copper and iron. If a definite chemical compound is formed the ratio C_m/C_n should be constant (C_m and C_n are the concentrations in millimoles of the metallic hydroxide and the non-electrolyte respectively). Table II gives the values of the above ratio.

TABLE II.

Amount of salt (in millimole).	Sugar. C_m/C_n .	Glycerol. C_m/C_n .
0·00768	0·00620	0·00056
0·01536	0·00636	0·00530
0·02304	0·00709	0·00032
0·03072	0·00526	0·00025
0·03840	0·00400	0·00022
0·04608	0·00335	—

The value of the ratio C_m/C_n does not remain constant. It first increases and then decreases throughout with an increase in the concentration of the salt solution. The fact that the value of the ratio C_m/C_n is not constant is distinctly in favour of the non-existence of any definite compound of thorium and the non-electrolytes.

Effect of Volume.

Tables III and IV give an idea about the effect of volume change on the amounts of sugar required to prevent precipitation of thorium hydroxide when caustic soda solution is added to a solution of thorium nitrate of different concentrations.

TABLE III.

NaOH=0·6 millimole.

Amount of salt (in millimoles).	Vols. of cane-sugar soln. necessary to prevent precipitation.	
	15 c.c.	25 c.c.
0·00768	1·25	1·24
0·01536	3·15	1·64
0·02304	4·33	3·25
0·03072	7·45	5·84
0·03840	10·73	9·62

TABLE IV.

NaOH = 0.6 millimole.

Amount of salt (in millimoles).	Cane sugar necessary to prevent precipitation (in millimoles).					
	12	15	20	25	30	35 c.c.
0.01536	2.20	2.15	1.84	1.64	1.48	1.10

From Table III it is seen that the amount of sugar required to inhibit the precipitation of hydroxide from the salt solution of a definite concentration in presence of a fixed amount of caustic soda varies with a change in the total volume of the system. Table IV shows that although the amounts of the metal ion and the alkali remain the same, the amount of sugar decreases with an increase in dilution of the system. This volume-effect can be explained in the following manner:—

At a smaller dilution the distances between the individual particles will be smaller than what they will be at a greater dilution and therefore the chances of collisions between the particles will be greater in the former than in the latter. Hence a greater amount of sugar will be required to inhibit the precipitation of the hydroxide at smaller dilutions. Moreover, water itself will act as a peptising agent at greater dilutions and, therefore, the particles will be disintegrated into finer ones thus making the whole system clearer than what it will be at smaller dilutions. This effect will also partly explain why smaller amounts of sugar are required to inhibit the precipitation of a particular amount of the hydroxide at higher dilutions.

The above results can also be explained on the basis of the fact that adsorption is greater from a dilute solution than from a concentrated one. The adsorption of the non-electrolyte being greater from a dilute solution than from the concentrated one less of the non-electrolyte will be required to inhibit the precipitation of the hydroxide in the former case than in the latter.

Amount of Alkali.

It was observed in the preliminary experiments that the amount of sugar or glycerol necessary to prevent the appearance of the hydroxide depended upon the amount of the alkali present in the system although the amount of the metal ion was kept constant. Some experiments were, therefore, tried to investigate this effect. The results of these experiments are given in Table V.

TABLE V.

Total volume = 25 c.c.

Amount of salt (in millimoles).	Cane sugar required to prevent the precipitation of hydroxide (in millimoles).					
	Amount of NaOH in millimoles.					
	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6
0.00768	15.1	1.52	1.24	1.24	1.24	1.24
0.01536	—	5.52	4.25	3.15	2.65	1.65
0.02304	—	15.10	9.82	7.21	5.70	4.20
0.03702	—	19.00	15.31	10.82	8.30	5.85
	Glycerol required to prevent the precipitation of hydroxide (in millimoles).					
	Amount of NaOH in millimoles.					
	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6
0.00768	3.10	2.12	1.41	1.0	1.0	1.0
0.01536	—	5.51	3.82	2.52	1.91	1.71
0.02304	—	20.10	15.12	11.60	8.88	6.31

It will be seen from Table V that when the amount of the metal ion is small the decrease in the amount of alkali is not continuous but soon reaches a minimum value which does not decrease further with any more increase in the amount of the alkali (as far as the maximum amount of the alkali tried in this experiment is concerned). This, however, is not found to be the case with higher concentrations of the metal ion. Although the precipitation of thorium hydroxide from a solution containing 0.03072 millimole of thorium nitrate could be prevented by the addition of 15.1 millimoles of cane sugar in the presence of 0.3 millimole of caustic soda, 19 millimoles of cane sugar were found to be insufficient for the purpose in the presence of 0.2 millimole of alkali. These results are in line with those obtained by Mehrotra (*loc. cit.*) and may be explained on the basis of the view that the non-electrolyte inhibits the precipitation of metallic hydroxide from its salt solution only in the presence of an excess of the alkali. It will thus be seen that neither cane sugar nor glycerol can inhibit the precipitation of the metallic hydroxide by itself in the

absence of an excess of the alkali. The fact that alcohols could not inhibit the precipitation of the hydroxide from its salt solution and that even sugar and glycerol could do so only in the presence of an excess of the alkali supports the conclusion arrived at in another paper ("Relation between purity of thorium hydroxide and its sensitisation by electrolytes," in course of publication) in that as these non-electrolytes coagulate the thorium hydroxide sol they should not be able to peptise it.

The fact that in the presence of increasing amounts of the alkali less and less amounts of the non-electrolyte are required to prevent the precipitation of a colloid can be explained on the ground that a greater amount of the alkali will exert a greater stabilising influence on the colloid and hence the amount of a non-electrolyte required to inhibit the precipitation of the metallic hydroxide will be less.

Summary.

1. The inhibition of the precipitation of thorium hydroxide from the solution of thorium nitrate in the presence of sugar, glycerol, urea, acetone, and methyl ethyl, and isopropyl alcohols when sodium hydroxide is added to it has been studied.

2. It is observed that of the above non-electrolytes only cane sugar and glycerol can inhibit the precipitation of the hydroxide and that the former is more effective in its action than the latter.

3. The amount of sugar or glycerol necessary to prevent the precipitation of the hydroxide, other conditions being same, is found to (a) increase with an increase in the amount of metal ion, (b) decrease with an increase in the dilution of the system—colloid + alkali + non-electrolyte + water, and (c) decrease with an increase in the amount of sodium hydroxide.